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Postcolonial Identity and the Role of Exile in Edward Said's Works: A Literary Exploration of Dislocation and Selfhood

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Abstract:

This research paper will study how Edward Said's works have explained the distortions of identity and cultural representations of colonised part of world by west or colonisers for the power structure. Said has involved himself into finding out the hybridity among the culture of a 'colonised' which is caused by the effect of colonialism; along with observing the resistance from the side of the colonised for preserving and perpetuating their own culture and history. This research paper will explore Edward Said's interpretation of the confusion of identity that happens to humankind when they transfer from one culture to another. The experiences and deeply-rooted every day challenges that are faced by colonised people are documented in works of Edward Said such as "*Orientalism*," "*Reflections on Exile*" and "*Culture and Imperialism*."

Keywords: Postcolonialism, Diaspora, Exile, Colonisers, Culture, Identity.

1.1 Introduction

The two most well-known works by Edward Said are his controversial reporting on the political situation in Palestine and his groundbreaking thesis "*Orientalism*," which transformed critical theory and had an impact on the emerging field of postcolonial studies.

International backing for the creation of the current state of Israel was based on the 1917 "Balfour Declaration," which reaffirmed "British support" for "the establishment in Palestine of a national home for the Jewish people." This claim was made by British Foreign Secretary Arthur James Balfour in a letter to leading Jewish supporter Lord Rothschild during World War I in an attempt to win Jewish support for the Allies. It served as the focal point of the effort to establish a Jewish state in Palestine. Balfour claimed that "*nothing shall be done which may prejudice the civil and religious rights of existing non-Jewish communities in Palestine,*" but in reality, the proclamation had the effect of denying the former residents of Palestine their own sovereignty. Many of the issues that have dominated Edward Said's work, such as identity struggles, the emphasis on imperial power and colonialist discourse, the criticism of political and cultural oppression, worries about the material conditions of thinking and writing, and discontent with prevailing models of literary and cultural theory, stem from this attempt to win Jewish support for the Allies in the First World War and its effects on the Palestinian people (Said, "*Orientalism*").

Born in 1935, Edward Said was raised in Cairo. He attended Victoria College, which was based on the prestigious public universities in Britain, St George's, and the American School. Said grew up in Cairo as a solitary and industrious youngster whose father was nearly fixated on the necessity of discipline in both work and education. He found great solace in reading books and Sunday classical music performances on the BBC. According to Said's 1999 memoir, "*Out of Place,*" he was somewhat of a "troublemaker" during that time. Feeling he had no hope in the British system, his parents moved him to Mount Hermon Prep School in Massachusetts after he was expelled from Victoria College in 1951. Said was a gifted student who spoke multiple languages and played the piano to performance levels, despite the fact that school in America was frequently challenging for him. After graduating from Princeton, he earned his doctorate in Joseph Conrad at Harvard before accepting a post as an

assistant professor of comparative literature at Columbia University. While attending Julliard School of Music, he was unsure about his desire to pursue a career as a concert pianist. However, he decided he was too intelligent and started a successful academic career. When the 1967 Arab-Israeli War started, Said was well on his way to becoming a famous but uninteresting professor of comparative literature. "That moment changed my life," he said. Abruptly, he was in a hostile climate against Arabs, Arab states, and Arab ideologies. The Arabs appeared to be "getting what they deserved," and he, a reputable scholar, had been picked out and rejected in a place where practically everyone supported Israel. Said was forced to face the paradox of his own situation following the 1967 conflict and how it was perceived in America; he was unable to maintain two identities, and the experience started to show in all aspects of his writing (Said "*Out of Place*").

1.2 Postcolonial Identity in works of Edward Said

The term "post colonialism" is commonly used to refer to all of the colonial era civilisations that were influenced by the imperial process. Post-colonialism denotes continued East-West concerns and dialogues since the beginning of the colonial period. It seeks to restore the identity of the "Independent Oriental Nations" by investigating the facts and studying and analysing the effects of colonialism. It includes works of literature from a number of former British colonies, including Canada, Australia, New Zealand, Nigeria, Kenya, India, Pakistan, and Jamaica. They are occasionally referred to as Third World countries. There are several assessments and discussions regarding theorists' claims regarding identity creation and its crisis in the postcolonial era, but there is a tacit agreement that the dilemma's existence and complexity constitute the main result and overt effects of colonialism. Foucault's discourse analysis approach was used by Edward Said (1978) to examine the writings of European orientalist concerning the "Orient," or conquered globe. According to Said, the dichotomy

between the West and the East shapes his view of identity and is "Eurocentric." By focusing on knowledge structures both within and between cultures, Foucault's post-structuralism abandoned the notion of cultures as systemic structures. It maintained that the way people are portrayed in discourse or conversation reflects the dominant knowledge regimes and their claims of truth, and that representation itself becomes a tool of power. He focuses on the idea that Western dominance determines one's identity. He sees truth as defined by those in positions of power; therefore, Western knowledge and power, or colonisers, enable them to assess and organize colonised knowledge on the basis that this gives them the authority to define knowledge using their power. They consider the colonists to be superior as a result of this idea. Therefore, the core idea of Said's argument is that colonial people are ensnared in the colonizer's belief system techniques and have successfully impacted the colonized through this justification. As a result, identity is constructed and organized within the parameters of Western or Occidental knowledge, making it impossible for colonial people to identify with themselves outside of this Orientalist perspective (Said, "*Orientalism*").

Ashcroft and Alohawa (1991) clarify Said's claim that the Western cultural foundations are in charge of recognizing these others by distinguishing subjects from masters. This justification so connects to Said's theory of identity development, in which he emphasizes "Eastern identity." The claim that the colonized should rebel against "Western power," reject the forced identity, and create their own is based on this argument, which Said made beginning with the publication of "Orientalism" and in a number of works anticipating on the significance of resistance in the postcolonial era. According to his imagination, the Western plan's empowerment basically resulted from the lack of opposition, which was the source of the Orient's subjugation and the outcome of 'Orientalist dominance.' As *"the last resistance we have against the cruel practices and treacheries that deform*

mankind's history," Said thus offers resistance during decolonization a more significant purpose (Said, "*Orientalism*")

Said claims that the 'West' always views the 'East' as an uncivilised, primitive "other" and considers itself to be civilised. The 'Orient' people are at risk from this other mindset. In addition, he queries "*why the West must teach the East how to be civilized and what constitutes civilization?*" The parameters for comprehending the truth are established by this query. He draws the conclusion that "The relationship between Occident and Orient is a relationship of power, of domination, of varying degrees of a complex hegemony." "*Knowledge is never innocent; it is always controlled by power;*" is a Foucauldian idea that informs Edward Said's 1978 book "*Orientalism.*" This power-knowledge relationship aids the occident in creating their own version of reality. The term 'orientalism' describes how Europe and the West perceive, find, and define 'the orient'. In the literary sense, it refers to Western discourse on the East in any field—academic, sociological, etc.—that does not have an Eastern equivalent. The result of this conversation is the development of a "textual world." It alludes to how the 'West' views the 'East' and how the occident looks east.

According to Said, there is a practice that places the 'West' in a superior position when examining the ontological and epistemological differences between the East and West. This practice is intentionally created in the West. According to Said, the occident seeks to take advantage of the 'Orient' in the name of humanising, illuminating, and civilising them. Said makes the "us" and "other" factors considerably more significant. Said argues that a strong coloniser has forced a language and culture on the colonised people or nation, and that the colonising system continues to be characterised by anarchy, coups, corruption, civil conflicts, and bloodshed imposed by the coloniser. The colonial language and culture are typically disregarded. But their primary goal is to skew the conquered culture and language so that the populace of the colonised country unknowingly serves the coloniser's interests.

Said discovers that the colonised society's practice of warped culture cannot psychologically tear down the wall of psychological imperialism. The growth of a new kind of imperialism is aided by deceptive writing produced by the 'West' for the 'East.' According to Said, it is incorrect to keep politics and history apart from literature and culture. Therefore, in order to comprehend the complicated hegemony, it is vital to examine both of them together (Said, "*orientalism*").

1.3 Representation of Exile by Edward Said

Since his untimely death in September 2003, Said has been lauded by many of his academic admirers for his many inspirational "gifts" to the world, his passion, courage, boldness; his role as an intellectual "lighthouse" in the murky Middle East politics; his dedication to global justice, ideas, and literature; and his evocation of the "pleasures of exile" that speaks "*powerfully to the experience of many [...] intellectuals.*" His political admirers, many of whom were in the Arab world, also expressed their deep admiration for him, calling him "this ferocious critic of imperialism, this staunch warrior against oppression," "the Palestinian's envoy to human conscience," the "universal Palestinian", the unique "mentor" with "a raging thirst for the recognition and validation" of the oppressed, an outstanding scholar and musician who brought "together the radical denunciation of cultural hegemonism with such a deeply felt commitment to universalis," an articulate advocate for Palestinian aspirations, and a just and compassionate enemy of Israel, whose passing was "a great loss to the 'Wretched of the Earth'" (Khar). These are heartfelt homages to a brilliant thinker and a model public intellectual, not merely courteous farewells. This sense of loss is shared by many African intellectuals because Said's work has had a significant impact on African studies. There would be broad sympathy for Samir Amin's commendation: "*I salute the subtle intelligence*

that allowed Said to debunk the Eurocentric projects hidden in the folds of Western scientific and fictional literature, which inform the dominant discourse on Orientalism" (Amin).

Exile as a temporal and spatial state of being, belonging, and being, as well as in its material and metaphorical contexts, has a significant impact on Said's personal, professional, and political existence. Egypt remained to be an important location where Said frequently returned, having spent a large portion of his early exile in Egypt and Africa. He gained a vital platform for his impassioned performances as the foremost public intellectual in Palestine and the Arab world from the "Egyptian" academic and popular media. Many African intellectuals have also been forced into exile, a destiny that has been welcomed by some and unwelcome by many others. Said's experiences and observations on exile render a chance to consider the dynamics and ramifications of African literary exile while also shedding light on the exiled state of the postcolonial world.

Written as a form of comfort while facing leukemia, the cancer that would ultimately claim his life, Edward Said's 1999 book *"Out of Place"* is a tribute to his youth, to exile, and to Egypt that is simultaneously heartbreaking, painful, and enjoyable. "The time of this book is intimately tied to the time, phases, ups and downs, variations in my illness," he reveals in a poignant paragraph. *"As I became weaker and experienced more infections and side effect episodes, this book became my means of creating anything in prose as I struggled with degeneration-related fears and pains in both my bodily and emotional lives"* (Said, *"Out of Place"*). Writing served as a means of recovery, remembrance, recreation, and a return to the enigmatic home of his childhood. Words and memories are summoned in all their solemn and polished intensity to make sense of an extraordinary, fragmented life that is always "out of place," suspended in exile, in a huge act of mental and physical bravery. A life of perpetual yearning for the affection and acceptance of one's parents, for the conveniences of belonging, and for the disruptions of frequent departures, arrivals, returns, and travels are all part of this

complex exile, which includes ontological, temporal, and spatial displacements as well as alienation from one's homeland, family, language, and continuities of self. "*An extraordinarily increasing number of departures have unsettled my life from its earliest beginnings,*" he adds with a caustic sense of humor mixed with melancholy. Nothing, in my opinion, more painfully and strangely describes "*my life than the numerous relocations from nations, cities, homes, languages, and situations that have kept me on the move for so long. I noted in After the Last Sky thirteen years ago that I usually bring too much with me when I travel, and that even a trip downtown necessitates carrying a briefcase full of stuff that are disproportionately greater in size and quantity than the trip's duration. After giving this some thought, I came to the conclusion that I had a hidden but unavoidable fear of not coming back* (Said, "*Out of Place*" 217).

Egypt is the place where he feels most at home. Cairo is listed as his residence when he leaves for the United States in the early 1950s to finish high school and later college. He longs for "*some friendly contact emanating from home, something to make an opening in the immediate fabric of loneliness and separation that I felt surrounding me.*" Mount Hermon High School, which is situated in what he describes as the "alienating and desolate" New England terrain. His life is rooted in Cairo's periods, both literally and figuratively. His sense of isolation is further heightened by the fact that even the changing of the seasons in America causes confusion: "*I missed our family's Cairo cuisine during school meals and kept calculating the seven-hour time difference (setting my bedtime alarm on Cairo time) since I wished to be back in Cairo. [...] Having come from a largely warm and dry region, I saw the transition from fall to winter with dread because it was something new to me. When I saw snow for the first time on November 1, 1951, my sixteenth birthday, I was disgusted and have never recovered. Despite my best efforts, I haven't discovered much to appreciate or like about snow since then*" (ibid). *Death for nice [...]. This made my time in America seem*

fleeting, and although though I was in the US for three-quarters of the year, I always attributed stability to Cairo (Said, "Out of Place"). But with disdain, he admits that this is not a childlike desire, the inevitable gap of rupture, to be forgotten as one ages, mellowed and dissipated by America's toxic charms in "*the extraordinary homogenizing power of American life,*" wherein the same television, clothing, ideological homogeneity, movies, newspapers, comics, etc., appeared to reduce the intricate interactions of everyday life to a minimal level of reflection in which memory is irrelevant.

For the rest of his life, he suffers from the agony of displacement, a festering wound that is impervious to time and external validation. He regrets: "*Even while I think I have no illusions about the 'better' life I may have had had I stayed in the Arab world or lived and studied in Europe, I still feel as though I am away from home to this day, as absurd as that may sound. On a certain way, this memoir is a recreation of the experience of leaving and fleeing out. Despite having lived in New York for thirty-seven years, I still feel provisional, which highlights the disadvantages more than the benefits I have gained.*" There were a lot of benefits. He highlights the wealth of intellectual chances he received during his education and subsequent academic career in the United States. He describes in ecstasy the cerebral joys that Mount Hermon satiated and encouraged, his zenith as a Princeton undergraduate, and the start of an outstanding academic career at Harvard as a graduate student.

This is his recollection of Princeton: "*Everything I have done as a scholar and educator has been built upon my readings in the history of philosophy, literature, and music. My mind was able to explore entire areas of learning with minimal self-consciousness at the time thanks to the Princeton curriculum's sedate comprehension. I only found myself going deeper, beyond the level of formal academic success, and starting to somehow create for myself a cohesive and independent attitude of mind when that learning came into contact with the inspiring critique of Szathmary or the visionary empowerment of Blackmur. During the*

first few weeks of my second year; I was aware that I was continuing to develop an early obsession with complexity and unpredictability, particularly and permanently in the various intricacies and ambiguities of speech and writing” (Said, “Out of Place”).

1.4 Discourse of Colonialism

Europe's experience of the Orient and the way it expressed that experience are both included in the discourse of Orientalism. Said attempts to characterise Orientalism mainly as an expression of power and knowledge by presenting it as a ‘meta-discourse’ in Foucauldian terms. He illustrates how knowledge of the defeated people was always necessary for the several interconnected discourses and institutions of colonial conquest. The Western nations relied on this understanding of the ‘Orient’ to justify and justify their aspirations to expand their empires. Said shows that the discourse of “*Orientalism*” views the ‘Orient’ and the ‘Oriental’ as objects that can be examined and comprehended, and "received knowledge" of these two regions has always been historically generated. The underlying premise of this objectification is that the ‘Orient’ is essentially monolithic. The ‘Occident’ is seen as a dynamic entity with an active history, whereas the ‘Orient’ has just a static one. In the end, the ‘Orient’ and ‘Orientals’ are viewed as passive research objects. By illustrating this- Said attempts to create a series of connections between the creation of subjects and colonialism via the formation of cultural identities. There are various levels and dimensions at which this ‘Oriental’ subject formation occurs. "*European culture gained in strength and identity by setting itself off against the Orient as a sort of surrogate and even underground self,*" as Said observes (Said, “*Orientalism*”).

In many ways, the "Oriental" is presented as a static, unchangeable other devoid of subjectivity and variation. They are distinguished from the "Occidental" subject in a remarkable way by this depiction of the Oriental as inferior, subdued, or in need of "Western" favor and guidance. Actually, this distinction helps Europeans define their own identities by

helping them see the binary opposition. Geographical imagination has always been the primary source of entities like the "Orient," and the authority usually attributed to the "Occident" is largely derived from the growth of knowledge about the "Orient:" *"Knowledge gives power; more power requires more knowledge, and so on in an increasingly profitable dialectic of information and control"* (Said, "Orientalism" 36).

The "Orientalism" describes how the 'Orientals' knowledge facilitates and benefits their administration. As a result, the 'Occident' must inevitably construct the 'Orient' as the "Other" in order to use this conflict to define and strengthen its own identity. According to Said, *"we shall have advanced a little in the process of what Raymond Williams has called the 'unlearning' of the inherent dominative mode"* if this binary, 'Orient' and 'Occident,' were to completely vanish. Without a range of cultural institutions and discursive practices, colonization probably would not have been possible. "Orientalism" provides ample evidence of this important lesson. It also highlights how "hegemony" plays a significant part in the process of colonial subjugation, which generally necessitates the agreement of the colonized people, demonstrated by their widespread acceptance of hegemonic discourses. Orientalism raises issues regarding how Western academics, tourists, and imperialists have constructed the Orient and Oriental people, highlighting the close ties between literature, history, and politics. This link between representation, knowledge, and power gives Said a lot of insight into the interaction between the West and the East. In the post-Enlightenment period, he aims to demonstrate that "European culture was able to manage and even produce--the Orient politically, sociologically, militarily, ideologically, scientifically, and imaginatively." Discourse was responsible for this taming or control of the Orient. It was made possible by Orientalism's language, which gave the Orient prestige and wisdom (Said, "Orientalism"). Again, through a variety of disciplines that dominated the political and cultural environment, these sources of power facilitated the political, economic, and military agendas of colonial

rule. With a strong emphasis on Foucauldian concepts of power, knowledge, and discourse, Said carefully analyses the western views of the Middle East that form the basis of his major works.

He blended these ideas with the Gramscian idea of hegemony. For those who had received Marxist training, the book's "Gramscian framework" was important. "Orientalism helped to define what it might mean to take empire as central to British society and history," as Catherine Hall states (Hall). She was attempting to trace the cultural relevance of "*Orientalism*," specifically in the setting of Britain. She contends that the notion of the English as an "imperial race" has always been connected to the English/British identities. According to Hall, decolonisation seemed to happen gradually, without much commotion or crisis around British identity issues. However, since the 1960s, there has gradually been a perceived crisis in English identity, especially due to the country's diverse non-white population. Furthermore, "race" was no longer lived at a distance: "*The geographical distance between the colony and the metropole was crucial to the rule of colonial difference, and makes British history in relation to 'race' and other-ness very different from that of the US*" (Hall).

The "others" who lived in Britain were frequently portrayed as foreigners and occasionally racialised. This new kind of racism was gradually adopted by Margaret Thatcher's "conservative party ideology." The nation was home to the empire, which posed a severe challenge to conventional ideas of what it meant to be British or English. This was Britain's post-colonial period, or "the time of transition," as Simon Gikandi refers to it, when the founding histories of the metropole began to unravel and imperial legacies began to haunt English and postcolonial identities, according to Catherine Hall. "Orientalism" provided a critical prism through which to view this change. In reality, "Orientalism" generated an attitude toward a spatial configuration of the world that contradicted the 'Eas'/'West' division

imposed by colonial thought. It added a political element to the debate over "Otherness" by advancing knowledge of how power relations influenced not just class and gender identities but also national, racial, and ethnic identities. The two icons of British colonialism, Lord Cromer and Arthur James Balfour, are examples of "Orientalists" that Said discusses in one of the subsections titled "Knowing the Oriental." With his unchanging sense of superiority, Balfour claims in defense of English sovereignty over Egypt, "*We know the civilization of Egypt better than we know the civilization of any other country;*" "*we are more familiar with it, we have a deeper understanding of it, and we have greater knowledge about it*" (Said, "*Orientalism*" 32).

In the House of Commons, Balfour used only tautological notions of the 'Orient' to defend England's dominance over Egypt. It also illustrates the relationship between dominance and knowledge. According to Said, "knowledge to Balfour" entails examining a civilisation from its inception through its height and eventual demise (32). Additionally, according to Balfour, "*Western nations show the beginnings of those capacities for self-government...having merits of their own as soon as they emerge into history.*" However, one never discovers evidence of self-government throughout the history of the entire Oriental people (32-33). Balfour then comes to the conclusion that England has a responsibility to govern Egypt. People like Balfour saw Egypt as an academic example of 'Oriental backwardness' and an argument for the legitimacy of 'Western imperialism,' in addition to being a colony. "*A subject race, dominated by a race that knows them and what is good for them better than they could possibly know themselves*" (35), was how they viewed 'Orientals.' Balfour's bizarre reasoning that "*Egypt requires, indeed insists upon, British occupation*" (34), which Said contends. Two major ideas that form the foundation of Balfour's thesis are power and knowledge. For Balfour, the British understanding of Egypt is the "real" Egypt since he never considers letting the Egyptian speak for himself. He appears

to be completely oblivious to the Orientalist belief that knowledge equates to dominance, authority, and power over something. Throughout his research, Said skill-fully illustrates this connection between power and knowledge. Since "Orientalism" is a fake, it always forces Western-created and controlled ideas of reality on the 'Orient.' This discourse did not emerge as an institution through direct coercion. The information about the Orient was disseminated as accurate facts. "*The ideology of Empire was hardly ever a brute jingoism; rather, it made subtle use of reason, and recruited science and history to serve its ends,*" writes Rana Kabbani, who agrees with Said (6). The more shrewed administrator Lord Cromer is lavishly praised by Balfour "*for his services...which have raised Egypt from the lowest pitch of social and economic degradation*" (Said, "*Orientalism*" 35). In a way, Cromer's "subject races" resemble Balfour's "Orientals." Balfour and Cromer both viewed themselves as guardian angels who guided Egypt to its current position of prominence. Cromer understood the perils of forcing the Oriental to adopt the logic of colonialism. Rather, he supported what modern thinker Noam Chomsky would refer to as "*manufacturing [their] consent.*"

In order to foster a closer relationship between the two races, the colonizer must recognize the limitations of the Oriental and strive for the "subject race's" satisfaction. He thought that Orientals were practically the same worldwide and that "subject races" lacked the intelligence to discern what was best for them (38). Cromer's ability to manage Egypt was aided by his scholarly and practical understanding of Orientals, including their race, character, culture, history, customs, society, and so on. Said cites the highly illuminating and patronizing chapter from Cromer's *Modern Egypt*, which states that the "Want of accuracy" is, in fact, the primary trait of the Oriental mentality. According to Cromer, the Oriental is "deficient in logical faculty" and "wanting in symmetry" when the European is a "natural logician" and a "close reasoner" (38). According to Cromer, "the Oriental generally acts, speaks, and thinks in a manner exactly opposite to the European" and "will often break down

under the mildest process of cross examination" (Said, "*Orientalism*" 39). "*A political vision of reality whose structure promoted the difference between the familiar (Europe, the West, "us") and the strange (Orient, the East, "them")*" is how Said describes "*Orientalism*." (43). The classic metaphysical division between the interior and the exterior permeated this conversation. The European was consistently portrayed as mature and logical in this hierarchical dualistic framework, whereas the 'Oriental' was portrayed as illogical and infantile. This was the result of the imperial power's constant control over the intellectual achievements of 'Orientalist' discourse.

1.5 Edward Said's Interpretation of Intellectual

Said is conscious of the European bias in Julian Benda's ideas about intellectuals, which grant them a universal area that was previously only available to Europeans. However, others have encroached on the territory after the decolonisation upheavals. The function of intellectuals has evolved along with the globe. Therefore, it is necessary to compare the intellectual to his historical, national, religious, or even continental identity. Said did think that "*some general notions about the individual intellectual...do seem to have more than strictly local application*" notwithstanding all the difference and otherness and the speeding phenomena of globalization (Said, "*Representations*" 20). Additionally, the intellectual is crucial to the rise of nationalism consciousness. "*The intellectual is obliged to use a national language not only for obvious reasons of convenience and familiarity but also because he or she hopes to impress on the language a particular sound, a special accent, and finally a perspective that is his or her own,*" Said asserts when discussing the perplexing issues of nationality and nationalism (20).

Simultaneously, he highlights the hidden perils inherent in language and exhorts the thinker to transcend national boundaries and speak a language that incorporates

transcendental ideals. Because "*dominant norms are so intimately connected to ... the nation, which is always triumphalist, always in a position of authority, always demanding loyalty and subservience rather than intellectual investigation and re-examination,*" it is the responsibility of the modern intellectual to challenge the status quo (27). According to Said, loyalty is a constant challenge for intellectuals. Since all intellectuals in one way or another are members of a national, religious, or ethnic society, this issue cannot be resolved easily. Unfortunately, Said notes, there has been a change from acquiescence and patriotic agreement to contestation and skepticism. Even if it is simple to give in and bow to the country, there are countless opportunities and challenges for the intellectual. Both the 'Third World' and the 'West' have demonstrated this. The idea of a unified national identity has been seriously challenged by the large-scale migration from the 'Third World' and the emergence of new social and cultural groups. But the critical consciousness has been overtaken by a form of pseudo-nationalism that poses as moral concern and patriotism. This essentially results in blind "loyalty to one's 'nation' before everything." Only intellectual treason and total moral bankruptcy remain at that moment ("The Treason").

The times demand that intellectuals be freed from these stifling restrictions of nationalism. "Never abating their criticism because of nationalism, even though they remained nationalists themselves" is how Said praises great intellectuals like Jose Marti and Tagore in this context (Said, "*Representations*" 31). In an interview, Said stated that "we belong to much larger identities, ones that are more healing, and more generously defined" in answer to inquiries on the notion of the revival of national identities, as well as the more constrained community or religious identities. Said also poses the question, "*Who cares about the labels of national identity anyway?*" in another context (410).

In "Reflections," Said notes: "*I talk about exile as an alternative to the mass institutions that rule contemporary life, not as a privilege. After all, exile is either something*

you are born into or something that occurs to you; it is not something you can choose. However, there are lessons to be learnt if the exile chooses not to sit on the sidelines tending to a wound: he or she needs to develop a rigorous subjectivity that is neither indulgent nor sulky” (Said, “Reflections” 184).

Said's exile is a mindset and a viewpoint, as well as a real and symbolic one. According to him, one of the requirements for intellectual representations is the condition of metaphysical homelessness. Because of this, it is necessary to only comprehend Said's intellectual representations in light of Palestinian history. Along with the passion that arises in the context of resistance and the creation of a humane and democratic future, this entails a proper knowledge of the absolute horrors connected to dispossession, exile, and occupation. The most crucial thing to keep in mind in this case is that Said's irrevocable loss of "home" and homeland never turns into the animosity of a nationalism that is restricted by religion or ethnicity. As Freud would say, he actually employs a "defense mechanism" to turn his experience of exile into political interventions and representations. The concept of exile is intrinsically tied to his philosophy of worldliness and the role of intellectuals. Said, a passionate cultural critic, believes that people write their own history in this world. He always highlights the importance of human agency in generating critical thinking in opposition to ideologies like Orientalism and imperialism. Since Said's self-construction as a critical intellectual was closely tied to his view that the individual can emerge through this labyrinth of discourses, this idea appears repeatedly in practically all of his writings.

To reveal the underlying ideologies of the dominant power structures, Said uses the contrapuntal technique that is inherent in the sensitivities of an exile, taking use of his in-between situation. "Said epitomizes the condition of exile and this sense of 'not belonging' has confirmed his own sense that the public intellectual needs to speak from the margin" (Ashcroft and Ahluwalia). According to Said, the idea of exile has drastically changed since

the late twentieth century, going from being the noble and exclusive punishment of exceptional people "to a cruel punishment of whole communities and peoples, often the inadvertent result of impersonal forces such as war, famine, and disease" (Said, "*Representations*" 35). Said is therefore more interested in the marginalised and mostly unaccommodated exiles, such the 'diasporic West Indian minorities' and Palestinians, "*whose presence complicates the presumed homogeneity of the new societies in which they live*" (37).

He is well aware that "the intellectual who considers himself-or-self to be a part of a more general condition affecting the displaced national community is therefore likely to be a source of volatility and instability, rather than acculturation and adjustment." As noted by Seamus Deane, "to be an exile at home and to be at home in exile is a fate that allows a writer to be apart from and immersed in the actuality." Intellectuals in exile face the challenge of not only physically leaving their place of origin, but also of figuratively isolating themselves. In terms of advantages, authority, and honors, these intellectuals are "*at odds with their [own] society and therefore outsiders and exiles*" (Said, "*Reflection*"). Said goes on to say: *The condition of exile, the state of never being fully adjusted, the constant sense of being outside the chatty, familiar world inhabited by natives, and the tendency to avoid and even detest the trappings of accommodation and national well-being are the best examples of the pattern that sets the course for the intellectual as outsider. In this metaphysical meaning, intellectual exile entails restlessness, mobility, and a persistent sensation of unease that disturbs others. Unfortunately, you can never completely settle in and become at one with your new home or circumstances, and you cannot return to a previous and possibly more stable state of being at home*" (39). This enables him to assert once more that the intellectual is typically "*happy with the idea of unhappiness*" in exile (39). Jonathan Swift is the historical figure who most embodies Said's description of such an intellectual. Swift fled to Ireland and created amazing work there, despite the fact that he was unable to regain his reputation in England. This is an

example of “*a mind flourishing, not to say benefiting, from such productive anguish*” (Said, “*Reflection*”).

1.6 Edward Said’s Experience in ‘Exile’

According to Said, Theodore Adorno is the most intriguing example of exile as he “*hated all systems, whether on our side, or theirs, with equal distaste*” (Said, “*Reflections*” 41). Adorno was an outsider who decided to live by different standards because of his Jewish heritage, his position as an Oxford professor, and his taste for fine culture. Before coming to the United States, he was inclined to live in ametaphysical exile and constantly opposed the perils of communism, mass-consumerism, popular culture and fascism. “*Minima Moralia: Reflections from Damaged Life*,” his autobiographical masterpiece, was written while he was living in exile in America. Surprisingly, Said’s own life and work appear to echo Adorno’s exile, his admiration of high culture, and his contempt for mass culture. Said keeps praising Adorno for his writing, which embodies the idea that an intellectual’s mind can never truly rest. When quoting Adorno, Said acknowledges the liminal area for the thinker: “*It is part of morality not to be at home in one’s home*” (42).

The intellectual gains a critical spirit as a result of this homelessness. Interestingly, Said likens an intellectual to someone who has been shipwrecked and learns to live with the earth instead of on it. He is more akin to Marco Polo, who never fails to see the fantastic and who is never a freeloader, conqueror, or raider but rather a traveler and a transient visitor (44). This exilic perspective also allows the intellectual to see situations as contingent rather than inevitable, since they are the result of a series of historical decisions made by men and women, as human-made facts of society, and not as natural or divinely given, making them unchangeable, permanent, and irreversible (45). Being out of place or in exile is a personal and professional fate, but for an intellectual, it is a necessary one. It was under this “executive

power of exile" that Auerbach was able to write *Mimesis* while in Istanbul. Said praises the renowned Italian philosopher Vico as the perfect illustration of this type of thinker. He paraphrases Vico's discovery from his book "*The New Science*," saying, "*The proper way to understand social reality is to understand it as a process generated from its point of origin, which one can always locate in extremely humble circumstances*" (45).

Said notes that "the intellectual in exile is necessarily ironic, skeptical, even playful-but not cynical," drawing inspiration from Vico and Auerbach (45). Additionally, he encourages eminent thinkers to embrace their new situation as "beginners," enabling them to lead unique, unorthodox, and quirky lives. Thus, Said transforms the concept of "exile into a normative mode of being" and extols the ideal of autonomy. According to Said, exilic thinkers have a number of benefits. First of all, because he must endure unstable conditions, the exile is constantly doubtful (Said, "Representations"). The exile perceives "things not simply as they are, but as they have come to be that way."

Thirdly, intellectuals who are exiled are freed from traditional concerns. In that state, the intellectual turns into a vigilant social critic, an advocate of unconventional ideas and values, and a counterbalance to the concessions made by the absorbed insider. An exile should view his fate as a form of freedom, a journey of discovery where he might get a special joy, rather than as a deprivation, since he is unable to choose a predetermined course. Exile is a state that allows one to explore despite obstacles, stand for change, be bold, and never stop moving. "Said attests to the emergence of critical consciousness in the experience of displacement," notes Asha Varadharajan. Said's focus in consciousness as the location of critique and resistance rather than conformity is consistent with this preference for exile (120).

Said questions the idea of power as a specific concept that has connotations of racism and absolute authority, being cautious not to take these lies at face value. Intellectuals should approach the emblems of power and knowledge with a healthy dose of skepticism and a critical awareness. When people are unable to escape the ideological conceptions of power, the state apparatuses will tend to keep supplying information that maintains or supports their positions of authority. To combat this situation, Said continually argued that intellectuals had an obligation to speak truth to power. Speaking the truth is challenging, though, because "truth" is seen as a very problematic and relative concept. Said rejects the idea that truth is "endlessly deferred" but is equally skeptical of simplistic conceptions of truth." Said observes that "speaking truth to power is no Panglossian idealism: it is carefully weighing the alternatives, picking the right one, and then ingeniously representing it where it can do the most-good and cause the right change" (Said, "*Representations*" 75). To put it another way, it entails the duty to expose the lies of influential liars to the public and to confront them with the truth. Said's concept of democratic critique, which entails "not only the right to dissent but the obligation to dissent, to break one's silence and passivity, to "*speaking truth to power*" without fear of censorship or violence," is something that W.J.T. Mitchell admires in his book "*Secular Divination: Edward Said's Humanism*."

One could contend that Said's development of the intellectual "speaking truth to power" is based on the modernist concept of the intellectual. In the postmodern era, when great narratives and personal signatures seem to have less sway than they did a century before, it is certainly possible to find inspiration in Said's concept of the intellectual in terms of courage, commitment, and the ability to speak truth to power. Despite its bleak tone, the intellectual's voice can readily identify with the realities of a movement, people's hopes, and the joint pursuit of an objective. Speaking truth to power can also be done in this way. The intellectual's role is to understand, interpret, and challenge authority rather than to solidify it

(Said, "*Reflections*" 502). According to Said, intellectuals should spearhead the critical examination of commonly accepted truths. He specifically cautions against the perils of some knowledge types, such as corporate thinking and nationalistic nationalism. His international outlook encourages acceptance of diversity and equality. Said cautions against all forms of self-aggrandizement and collective pride in his evaluation of Samuel Huntington's "*The Clash of Civilizations*." As Conrad rightly noted, the practice of rivalry and conflict served the real objectives of self-aggrandizement, power, conquest, treasure, and unfettered self-pride.

Said's numerous exhortations regarding the character and function of intellectuals, which have a great deal of resonance from his personal life, Said has amassed a sizable and varied following. He believed that intellectuals should distance themselves from rigid dogma or traditional party lines. He urges people to leave the boundaries of institutions and material forces and to overcome all the obstacles imposed by their nationality, language, and background. Finding relative independence from these influences is the primary intellectual responsibility, which is why Said describes the intellectual as "exile and marginal, as amateur, and as the author of a language that tries to speak the truth to power" (Said, "*Representations*"). It is accurate to state that Said's "*Representations*" may be an exegesis of his own life and status as an intellectual and writer. As he states: "Intellectuals are those who have a vocation for the art of representing, whether that be through speaking, writing, teaching, or appearing on television, he fully supports his own views on representations. And that profession is significant insofar as it is publicly identifiable and entails both danger and dedication, bravery and vulnerability" (10).

Said received a lot of criticism for these audacious portrayals. His office at the University was set on fire, and he got several death threats after the Jewish Defence League labeled him a Nazi in 1985. Because they believed his opinions were too "liberal on the

question of Palestine and the idea of co-existence between Israeli Jews and Palestinian Arabs," radical left-wing nationalists also targeted him (Said, "*Reflections*" 564).

When Said wrote more forcefully about his disagreements with Arafat and his group of supporters in 1993, as the official spokesperson for the Palestinian resistance, a complicated situation developed. He was immediately branded "anti-peace" when he contended that the "Oslo Accord" amounted to surrender and a process that would lead to more hostilities. He was, as it happened, entirely right. He later criticized Arafat's poor leadership, asking, "*What kind of leader is this? Arafat is finished. Why don't we accept that he is unable to organize, direct, or carry out any action that would be advantageous to anyone beyond himself and his Oslo allies, who have reaped material rewards from his people's suffering? the abandonment of Arafat.*" Said's straightforward honesty and integrity probably allowed him to stand outside the bubble that shielded or accepted some of his contemporaries (Said, "*Reflections*")

In the context of the global economy and neoliberalism, Said recognizes the scope of the intellectual problem. Through his commitment to the theory of historical reconstruction, Said brings attention to "subterranean histories," which contain the real truth that is often hidden. "*Said takes active political positions in his critical writings, in contrast to Jean-Paul Sartre's negative intellectual, who very conveniently turns a concrete situation into an abstraction*" (Walia). His portrayal of the intellectual captures his persuasive understanding of what may be unique to intellectual endeavours. He views intellectuals as morally upright members of society. Said emphasizes the part writers play in opposing the prevailing type of power structures in addition to the role of intellectuals. The creation of a national cultural heritage, the restoration of native idioms, and the reimagining and re-figuring of local histories, geographies, and communities were all made possible by writers, according to Said in a 1990 essay. As a result, literature not only inspired aggressive resistance to external

intrusions but also made a significant contribution as a creator, shaper, and illuminating force within the colonized people's territory.

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